

INNOVATIVE TEACHING OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE USING THE DICTIONARY METHOD, IN PARTICULAR THE DICTIONARY OF PARONYMS

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ABSTRACT

The conducted research, reflected in this scientific article on the importance of using the dictionary method, in particular paronyms, during the lessons of the Native Language, clearly and clearly demonstrates to us that this method of language learning, being traditional and rather old, is still very effective if you adhere to existing special methods and techniques for using the language learning method based on book dictionaries. This teaching technique can become quite innovative and interactive, if from the usual "cramming" new words to make an interesting, rich learning process filled with various interactive tasks and exercises that require group work and active verbal interaction between students and also with the teacher as the leader, guiding leader of the lesson. The article consists of the following sections: abstract, key words, actuality, aim, materials and methods, results and discussion, conclusion, references.

Actuality

It is currently extremely important to teach Native Language subject efficiently to schoolchildren. Nevertheless, the modern educational process can be complicated due to the decline of national culture and the fact that schoolchildren's speech consists mostly of street words, jargon and finally so called "teenagers slang".

According to my point of view, the mentioned study crisis that consists of the decline in the academic performance among pupils at school, is caused by insufficient mother tongue's pedagogical teaching. Taking into consideration my vast educational experience and, therefore, pedagogical expertise, I tend to follow and support the most traditional way of languages' learning, that view that should include extra study activity by means of various study dictionaries, that include explanatory, phraseological dictionaries, dictionaries of synonyms, antonyms and, of course, paronyms. One of the key objectives of this dictionary-based way of language learning lies in enriching pupils' lexicon; Another academic purpose of the mentioned above language learning method is to improve their communicative abilities -

both oral and written ones. Its main motives conclude in the thesis, claiming that the larger the vocabulary, the more accurately and rapidly the learning material may be comprehended and mastered.

Undoubtedly, one of the main researches of the lexicology of the Uzbek language is related to determining the interaction and influence of the internal and external aspects of the word. Among the phenomena directly related to this issue are synonymy, homonymy, antonymy, polysemy, variant and paronymy [1, p. 23]. The next two lexical-semantic categories have not been extensively studied in Uzbek linguistics, and paronymy remains an under-examined field in general linguistics.

Paronyms (para... and Greek onyma – name, name) - words with similar pronunciation, sound and morpheme structure, different or partially close lexical meanings. The phenomenon of the existence of such words in speech is called paronymy. The problem of paronymy arises as a result of deliberately bringing paronyms together in speech or using them knowingly/unknowingly, without distinguishing their meanings, and creates speech nonsense. Usually, the fields of speech culture and stylistics specifically study issues related to the correct use of paronyms.

Aim

The fundamental objective of the presented scientific experimental work carried out within the framework of the scientific-pedagogical research aimed at researching the problem of using the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in the native language classes of secondary schools is to determine the linguo-pedagogical and linguo-methodical foundations of creating Uzbek academic (educational) dictionaries, including the "Paronyms educational dictionary" based on the traditions of world educational lexicography, to determine the "Paronym o" for the native language classes of general secondary schools. It was defined as the development of the methodology of creating and using the vocabulary. Based on this goal, the following tasks were defined:

1. To substantiate the organizational and practical ideas of using the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in the mother tongue classes of general secondary schools.
2. Selection of effective methods for using the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in the mother tongue classes of general secondary schools.
3. Formation of a special methodology for the use of the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in the mother tongue classes of general secondary schools.
4. To create the necessary pedagogical conditions that ensure the effective assimilation of the use of "Paronyms educational dictionary" in the Native Language classes of general secondary schools.
5. One of these is the development of the methodology of using the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in the mother tongue classes of general secondary schools.

Paronyms are not a linguistic phenomenon. At the speaking stage, indiscriminate use of paronymic pairs (that is, using one instead of the other), their confusion (confusion), in fact, occurs as a result of the lack of sufficient mastery of the lexical standards of the given language, as well as the inability to distinguish the meanings of words, and indifference to their own speech [2, p. 46].

Materials and methods

It is necessary that the materials given in the explanatory dictionary of paronyms correspond to the achievements in Uzbek linguistics in all respects, and in particular, the theory of paronymy should be seen in practice. In this regard, V. V. Dubichinskiy, S. V. Lebedova, I. L. Vorontsova, E. Y. Balalayeva, A. I. Olkhovskaya, I. Fedorov, M. A. Shakhmatov, G. A. Miller, V. V. Peek, K. Felbaum, K. Petrova, etc.) and the results of research conducted on our national vocabulary (for example, B. Bahridinova, Z. Rakhmatova, Z. Rajabova, etc.). Ensuring scientificity in the compilation of the "Paronyms educational dictionary". The anthropocentric trend developed in Uzbek linguistics in the next 10-15 years should be reflected in the explanatory dictionary of paronyms.

During my research work I also analyzed the textbooks of T. A. Ladyzhenskaya, M. T. Baranov, L. A. Trostentsova; M. M. Razumovskaya, S. I. Lvova to identify tasks and exercises aimed at working with dictionaries in Russian language lessons. In these tutorials, we can see that the authors offer various ways and methods to implement the work with dictionaries.

According to Ernest Begmatov: "The development of the Uzbek language during the period of independence and the experiences of defining its linguistic standards show that the involvement of people in the social life and practice of the language, the work of its conscious management should be scientifically based, its theoretical principles and rules should be developed, and one should not indulge in excessive emotions and fake linguism in this matter." [3].

Some ways of using dictionaries in Native Language classes are listed below:

I. You have to master and fully understand the term-"word interpretation".

This is, from our point of view, the most effective technique for learning new words efficiently. In order to really effectively apply this method in the learning process, the teacher must first explain the structure of the teaching dictionary and its correct use independently during the lesson.

The chosen method requires the following tasks:

- 1) After explaining the basic use and principles of the dictionary, the teacher should direct the students to it in order to ensure the practical use of the acquired knowledge and to independently search for the necessary information.
- 2) Encourage students to consult the dictionary on their own for explanations, spellings and other words;
- 3) Start each lesson with word study and oral dictation.
- 4) Dictionaries of all types are reviewed, followed by an exercise of identifying dictionaries to note down.

The editing method is then based on morphological analysis. Morphological analysis is valuable because it forces students to think about the meanings of the morphemes that make up words. When they encounter an unfamiliar word, they will have no difficulty in identifying how a particular word is formed in order to understand its meaning.

Results and discussion

Now, let us move to the section results and discussion. The obtained practical outcomes consist of mainly empiric tasks and exercises for schoolchildren of comprehensive and secondary schools. The following exercises can be used to apply this pedagogical technique:

- 1) Teachers encourage students to determine the meaning of the word after the morphological analysis of the word;
- 2) giving students visual examples of the different meanings of the word depending on the morpheme of the root; and
- 3) Students can find and understand the meaning of ambiguous words by choosing synonyms/paronyms. Through this technique, students learn the basic properties of synonyms/paronyms and the dangers of using synonyms. Learning paronyms helps students to correct their written mistakes and to structure their oral speech [4, p. 412].

The following types can be used to make use of this technique:

- 1) Find pairs of synonyms in the exercises suggested by the teacher;
- 2) Write essays using synonyms and avoiding repetition; and
- 3) analyzing and correcting reports containing speech errors. What can be very interesting is the translation method.

Recognize loanwords and help determine their meaning and origin. A dictionary can help you know the correct pronunciation of borrowed words. To use this technique, the following tasks need to be undertaken:

- 1) Look up the meaning of the quoted word using a dictionary;
- 2) Read a text in Russian in which a foreign word that has come into use in the Uzbek language is used.

In this technique it is important to explain the situation to the student. In other words, if students see any symbol above a word, they should explain the interpretation of the word below. By learning the interpretation of the word, students will better understand where and how the word is used.

This technique can be used in the following ways.

- 1) Reading a text and practicing the underlined explanations so that students can choose the correct context for the underlined word;
- 2) Reading scientific texts and matching the word with its correct use in the text.

To sum up the section results and discussion of the given scientific research it's essential to allocate and determine organizational forms of pedagogical activity during the classes of Native Language subject, using academic dictionaries, particularly comprising paronyms:

I. Short lecture. Through it, students will be given information about the basics of the subject "Mother language" and the use of educational dictionaries in their acquisition, the use of the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in creating theoretical and practical knowledge on word pairs that are confused in pronunciation, and the creation of the "Paronyms educational dictionary". The mini-lecture is organized by the teacher of the subject "Native Language" [5, p. 17].

II. Discussion. With the help of this form of pedagogical activity, the attitude of the students of the 5-11th grades of general secondary schools towards the use of the "Paronyms educational dictionary", their need to determine this quality, their interest, their behavior in mastering the basics of the "Mother language" educational subject, creativity, the essence of attention focused on mastering the use of educational dictionaries, students within this educational subject A dialogue is organized between teachers and learners about the factors affecting the effective mastering of the use of the "Paronym educational dictionary".

III. Training. This form of pedagogical activity, in the form of a practical demonstration, serves to promote the ideas of effective use of the "Paronymil educational dictionary" in students, to form and develop the skills and competencies of continuous use of educational dictionaries based on these ideas. The most important feature of adaptive training is the joint performance of each action by students under the guidance of the teacher, which requires the constant use of educational vocabulary. In other words, training helps students to turn the skills of regular use of academic vocabulary into their habits.

IV. Practical training. This form of pedagogical activity, like training, serves to acquire creative skills and competencies by students. In contrast to training, in practical training, students independently complete the educational tasks presented by the teacher.

V. Skill classes. Workshops, such as training and practical exercises, serve to promote the ideas of effective use of the "Paronymil educational dictionary" by students, and to create the necessary conditions for the acquisition of skills and qualifications for the regular use of educational dictionaries. This form of pedagogical activity differs from training and practical training in some aspects. The main difference is that master classes are based on the practical demonstration of their work experience by a specialist with high professional competence in a specific field.

More of effective teaching methods using dictionaries are presented below:

Questionnaire. In the course of the research, a questionnaire survey was organized in order to determine the students' ability to use educational dictionaries. The questionnaire was prepared in two forms: 1) for respondents-students; 2) for a practitioner-teacher. Questions were included in both forms of the questionnaire, allowing to diagnose and evaluate the ability of the respondent-students to use educational dictionaries. The main attention was paid to determining the factors that ensure that the respondent-students have the ability to use educational dictionaries and the level of their influence. "Random associations" method. This method is designed to develop students' ability to use educational dictionaries by writing down four or five randomly selected words and searching for their dictionary meaning in the dictionary [6, p. 221].

The stages of using the method are as follows: 1) students of the class selected for the experiment are divided into two or four groups; 2) the respondent-students of the first group read a poem (or a short story) of their choice (provided that the poem (or story) contains paronymous words as much as possible); 3) the respondent-students of the second group find paronymous words from the text and find its meaning in the dictionary (they look for synonyms, antonyms (if any) of the word paronym; 4) for the first group, the respondent-students of the second group read a poem (or short story) with a paronym; 5) for the analysis of the selected paronyms, the "Dictionary of Paronyms" must be consulted, and in this regard, the speed of the students and the ability to work with the dictionary will be evaluated.

The special methodology for the development of using the "Paronyms educational dictionary" in Native Language classes has the following structural table

Table 1.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion of this article, I formed several basic theoretic-practical postulates, that are given below:

1. In this work, the use of dictionaries as a means of forming communicative competence was considered and justified, since Dictionaries are an integral part of language learning, especially when it comes to the mother tongue. Thanks to the work with dictionaries, the student's vocabulary is enriched. The formation of communicative competence is very important for the student. By communicative activity we mean the ability to use languages in the process of communication. With the help of this competence, the student will be able to accurately express his thoughts both orally and in writing.
2. I proposed innovative, interactive techniques for working with dictionaries in the lessons of the native language (Uzbek language). Working with dictionaries in such language classes is necessary to enrich the vocabulary of students and the implementation of communicative competence. We have identified such techniques as: I. Short lecture; II. Discussion method; III. Training; IV. Practical training; V. Skill classes.
3. I have developed a set of tasks aimed at working with various types of dictionaries, with which the teacher can diversify the educational process due to the lack of diverse, interesting, modern vocabulary exercises.

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